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KMT2B is activated in response to ERBB2 growth factor inhibition and is associated with resistance to doxorubicin.

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Epigenetic changes acquired following treatment with a chemotherapy may be a specific epigenetic change associated with that chemotherapy or an epigenetic change likely broadly associated with resistance to chemotherapy. Here we describe KMT2B as a gene product induced following growth factor inhibition in human cells and following exposure to doxorubicin chemotherapy associated with resistance.